

1 **Ambient air pollution and depression – A protocol for a systematic review and meta-**
2 **analysis**

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8
9 **Abstract**

10
11 **Background:** Ambient air pollution (AAP) is a significant global health hazard associated with
12 various non-communicable diseases and ecological threats. While the impact of AAP on
13 physical health is well-documented, its association with mental health, particularly depression,
14 has gained attention in recent years. However, existing evidence remains inconclusive and often
15 lacks consideration for regional differences in air pollution composition and climate.

16 **Objectives:** This protocol outlines a systematic review and meta-analysis aimed at updating
17 existing evidence on the relationship between short- and long-term exposure to selected air
18 pollutants (NO₂, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, O₃, and BC) and depression outcomes. Additionally, it seeks to
19 investigate potential regional variations in this association.

20 **Methods:** The review will adhere to PRISMA guidelines. Eligible studies include
21 epidemiological and human exposure studies reporting on the association between ambient air
22 pollution and depression in human populations. Comprehensive search strategies were
23 developed in collaboration with a research librarian. Two-stage screening and data extraction
24 processes will be conducted independently by reviewers. Risk of bias will be assessed using
25 the OHAT tool for observational studies. GRADE will be utilized to assess the quality of
26 evidence. Data analysis will involve meta-analyses stratified by exposure period and region
27 using random-effect models.

28 **Conclusion:** This systematic review and meta-analysis aim to provide updated and
29 regionspecific insights into the association between ambient air pollution and depression,
30 contributing to a better understanding of this critical public health issue.

31
32 **Keywords:** depression, air pollution, public health, environment

33 **1. Introduction**

34 The rapid urbanization and industrialization of the modern world has led to a significant
35 increase in ambient air pollution (AAP) levels especially in Asia (Srivastava, 2022) and while
36 there have been decreasing trends of some air pollutants it is still a significant health burden
37 (Sigsgaard & Hoffman 2024). AAP has been widely recognized to be a risk factor for
38 noncommunicable diseases such as cardiovascular diseases, cancers, and respiratory illnesses
39 (Cohen et al., 2017; WHO, 2021). Thus, air pollution stands as a significant global threat to
40 public health, contributing to approximately 7 million premature deaths each year, with 4
41 million attributed to AAP (WHO, 2021). Moreover, air pollution emerges as a primary driver
42 of climate change, posing a direct threat to our ecosystems (WHO, 2021). Clean air is rightfully
43 acknowledged as a human right essential to health, leading the World Health Organization
44 (WHO) to develop guidelines for air quality aimed at tackling this pervasive issue (WHO,
45 2021). AAP is a multifaceted mix of various pollutants, encompassing particulate matter (PM),
46 gaseous pollutants, as well as metallic and organic compounds (Nathanson, 2023). Particulate
47 matter (PM) is commonly categorized into PM_{2.5} (particles with an aerodynamic diameter
48 smaller than, or equal to, 2.5 μm) and PM₁₀ (particles with an aerodynamic diameter smaller
49 than, or equal to, 10 μm). Sources of ambient air pollution are diverse and can originate from
50 both natural and anthropogenic activities.

51 Public health or policy reports rarely include mental health consequences of air pollution, partly
52 due to insufficient evidence, but also due to the complexity of establishing an association
53 between mental health and air pollution (King et al., 2022). There is emerging evidence to
54 suggest that AAP adversely affects mental health. Recently, research within this topic has been
55 expanding, especially for depression (Buoli et al., 2018; Kim et al., 2016). Among mental
56 health disorders, depression is notably widespread and bears the greatest burden of disease
57 (Saloni Dattani et al., 2023). A condition closely linked to depression in terms of symptoms,
58 yet has distinct features is postpartum depression. Despite the high incidence of the condition,
59 research on this topic has been notably scarce (Bauman et al., 2020). Previous epidemiological
60 studies as well as systematic reviews have shown there is an association between AAP and
61 depression/PPD (Borroni et al., 2022; Braithwaite et al., 2019; Duan et al., 2022; Fan et al.,
62 2020; Liu et al., 2021; Shih et al., 2021). Also, studies have found that even short-term exposure
63 to AAP can cause exacerbation and trigger depressive episodes (Li et al., 2020; Ma et al., 2024;
64 Wang et al., 2018). However, studies are not unequivocal, with several not finding an
65 association (Kim & Kim, 2017; Wang et al., 2014; Zhao et al., 2019).

66 A recent meta-analysis (Borroni et al., 2022) included original studies published until May 20,
67 2021. The first aim of our review is to update this meta-analysis as several large
68 epidemiological studies on this topic have been published since then, including nine western
69 cohorts (Fu et al., 2022; Gao et al., 2023; Gładka et al., 2022; Li et al., 2023; Motoc et al., 2023;
70 Petkus et al., 2022; Qiu et al., 2023; Wu et al., 2022; Yang et al., 2023) as well as large cohorts
71 from Asia (Ji et al., 2023; Jiang et al., 2023; Khosrorad et al., 2022; Ma et al., 2024; Wang et
72 al., 2023; Wang et al., 2021; Yuan et al., 2023; H. Zhang et al., 2022; X. Zhang et al., 2022).
73 The second aim is to investigate whether the association between air pollution and depression
74 vary in different regions of the world. Since the chemical composition of air pollution, PM size
75 and distribution and regional climate vary widely with geographic location, it can be
76 problematic to compare studies from different regions and produce combined effect estimates
77 (de Hoogh et al., 2013; Yang et al., 2018).

78

79 **2. Objective**

80 We will assess the evidence on the relationship between short- and long-term exposure to
81 selected air pollutants (NO₂, PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, O₃, and BC) and depression outcomes. We will do
82 this by addressing the following research question that was formulated according to PECO
83 framework (Participant, Exposure, Comparator and Outcome): **“Is the exposure to ambient
84 air pollution associated with the risk of depression?”**

85

86 **3. Methods**

87 In this study, the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
88 (PRISMA) guidelines will be utilized (PRISMA, 2009).

89

90 *Eligibility criteria*

91 PECO statement:

92 **Populations:** Any human population

93 **Exposures:** ambient (environmental) air pollution, both short-term and long-term of the
94 following pollutants, both measured and modelled: Nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), particulate matter
95 (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀), ozone (O₃) and black carbon (BC).

96 **Comparator:** humans exposed to higher levels of ambient air pollution compared with those
97 exposed to less. The association needs to be reported quantitatively, using risk estimates such

98 as odds ratio (OR), hazard ratio (HR) or relative risk (RR) for exposure categories with their
99 concentration ranges reported, or per (x-fold) unit increase in exposure.

100 **Outcome:** diagnosis of depression, or postpartum depression, either from clinical or insurance
101 registers, self-reported doctor's diagnosis ("have you ever been told by a medical professional
102 that you have depression?") or by a clinicals assessment, including application of depression
103 test questionnaires. Additionally, for studies with the exacerbation of depression as an outcome,
104 could be reported using number of hospital visits, change in medication use or change in the
105 severity of depression.

106 **Types of studies:** epidemiological (e.g., follow-up, case-control and cross-sectional studies,
107 but not ecological design studies) including exposure assessment providing for an exposure
108 effect analysis. Only peer-reviewed published studies will be considered for the data synthesis.

109 **Exclusion criteria:** Studies which are not primary research studies, studies where the outcome
110 depression is only included in a larger outcome group such as "mental health disorders", studies
111 where the outcome is collected through self-diagnostic tools with no clinical input on the
112 diagnosis. Studies where the exposure is exclusively indoor air pollution or occupational
113 exposure thus making it challenging to distinguish the effects of air pollution from the other
114 influencing factor. Studies including persons with depression at baseline, except for the
115 outcome "depression exacerbation".

116 No language or publication year exclusion criteria will be used. However, title and abstract
117 searches in the databases require English terms.

118

119 *Search strategy*

120 Based on the PECO statement, the search strategy was developed in collaboration with a
121 research librarian. Search strings for the bibliographic databases Pubmed, Cinahl, Scopus and
122 Web of Science are shown in Appendix A. Additionally, relevant publications will be identified
123 by searching references from related studies and reports. Reference managing, screening and
124 data extraction will be done using the software Covidence (<https://www.covidence.org/>). The
125 search strategy is based on the combination of terms for ambient air pollution with different
126 terms for depression, using controlled vocabulary, such as MeSH terms. Furthermore, given
127 the potential variation in the thesaurus terms, the search strategy was adapted to each database.
128 No language filter will be applied to ensure a greater probability of including all the studies

129 addressing the research question of interest in this systemic review and to minimize selection
130 bias (Higgins et al., 2019). Finally, when all studies have been transferred to Covidence, before
131 the manual screening process, duplicates will be removed through an automatic tool in
132 Covidence.

133

134 *Selection process*

135 For this review a comprehensive and systematic approach will be utilized to identify relevant
136 studies that meet the eligibility criteria above and will be done by two reviewers in Covidence.
137 The title and abstract of each record will be screened. In cases where there is a discrepancy
138 among the reviewers, the study will move to the second stage (full-text screening).

139 During the second stage, studies that pass the initial title and abstract screening will undergo a
140 full-text review. In the appearance of a conflicting assessment among the reviewers during this
141 process, and if the two reviewers cannot reach consensus, a third reviewer will be consulted to
142 make the final determination. A record will be excluded when it does not adhere with the
143 inclusion criteria or if it contains an exclusion criterion. The exclusion reported based on failing
144 to meet the criteria for “Population”, “Study design”, “Exposure”, “Outcome”, “Comparator”,
145 and “other”, with a further description of the exclusion reason. The compilation of studies
146 excluded during the title and abstract screening or the full-text screening stage, along with the
147 rationale for their exclusion, will be provided in the supplementary material and in a PRISMA
148 Flow Diagram.

149

150 *Quality assessment*

151 The risk of bias (ROB) assessment will be done independently by two reviewers. Again, if
152 consensus is not reached, a third reviewer will be involved to adjudicate the final assessment.
153 This review will use the Office of Health Assessment and Translation (OHAT), which is a well-
154 recognized risk of bias tool for observational studies (OHAT, 2015). This tool includes 6
155 domains of selection, confounding, performance attrition/exclusion bias, detection, selective
156 reporting and has a total of 11 questions. For each domain, studies will be rated as “low risk”,
157 “probably low risk”, “probably high risk”, “high risk” or “not applicable” according to the
158 instructions listed in Appendix B.

159 Following the OHAT handbook's recommendations, we will implement a 3-Tier system to
160 synthesize study findings, particularly when there is variation in the risk of bias (ROB) across
161 studies or different analyses within the same study. This approach is based on three key criteria:
162 confidence in randomization and concealment of subject allocation, confidence in
163 characterizing exposure, and confidence in assessing outcomes. The application of the tier
164 approach within a single study may yield varying results, influenced by factors such as the
165 nature of the outcome, type of exposure, and the method used for exposure assessment. To
166 depict the distribution of risk of bias (ROB) across studies or analyses, heat maps can be
167 generated for visualization purposes.

168 A **Tier 1** study must exhibit "definitely low" or "probably low" ROB for the key criteria all
169 other criteria. A **Tier 3** study, on the other hand, scores "definitely high" or "probably high"
170 ROB for the key criteria and all other criteria. A **Tier 2** study does not meet the stringent criteria
171 for Tier 1 or Tier 3, falling somewhere in between (NTP, 2019).

172

173 *Data extraction*

174 During the data extraction phase, the process will follow a similar approach to the screening
175 phase. Two reviewers will each evaluate the entire set with each study being independently
176 assessed. The following information will be extracted: study characteristics (author name,
177 publication year, study design and location), participant characteristics, list of exposures,
178 outcome (definition and collection method) and effect estimates (RR/OR/HR) with their
179 confidence intervals. Conflicts will be settled by consensus if possible. Otherwise, a third
180 reviewer will be acquired to resolve it. If the studies present with unadjusted and adjusted effect
181 estimates, the one that is controlled for most potential confounders will be chosen. Should any
182 uncertainty arise during data extraction, the corresponding author on the study will be contacted
183 to seek any clarification. A draft of the data extraction form to be implemented in Covidence is
184 shown in Appendix C.

185 In cases where depression diagnosis was determined through various methods, such as doctor's
186 diagnosis, questionnaire, medical usage, clinical assessment based on International
187 Classification of Disease (ICD) or self-reporting, we will prioritise the most objective method
188 where ICD is considered gold standard. In some studies, different lag times are used to
189 determine the important exposure windows. These lag patterns can be reported either as single
190 lag days or cumulative lag windows. We will use or report the most relevant lags in this paper.

191 *Standardization of data*

192 The included studies will most likely report their effect estimates using different measures
193 which usually are either risk ratios (RR), hazard ratios (HR) or odds ratios (OR). We will
194 collectively refer to these as relative risk measures. If studies report slopes, we will transform
195 these to relative risks by exponentiation. Furthermore, for comparability, each adjusted effect
196 estimate extracted from included studies, along with their 95% CI will be standardized to a
197 fixed air pollution concentration increment of 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$.

198 Studies reporting results only for exposure categories, we will standardize the results to 10
199 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ by using the median (if not available: mean) of the exposure categories. If the highest
200 category is reported without a range, median or mean, the width of the previous exposure
201 category is assumed.

202

203 *Synthesis (meta-analysis)*

204 For each exposure-outcome pair with two or more studies that meet the eligibility criteria, we
205 will assess whether a quantitative synthesis in form of a meta-analysis is meaningful, given
206 similarities in study populations, outcome definitions, and exposure assessments. If it is
207 deemed that a meta-analysis is not appropriate, results will be synthesized qualitatively.

208 For the exposure (NO_2 , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, PM_{10} , O_3 , and BC) and outcome pairs for “depression incidence”
209 and “PPD”, we will stratify meta-analyses by exposure period: short-term (equal to or less than
210 1 month) and long-term (more than 1 month). For the exposure (NO_2 , $\text{PM}_{2.5}$, PM_{10} , O_3 , and
211 BC) and outcome pairs “depression exacerbation”, we will only assess short-term exposure
212 periods. We will compute an overall association, as well as further stratify by region (Europe,
213 North America, South America, Africa, Asia, others), when meaningful.

214 All the statistical analyses for this systematic review will be conducted using the latest version
215 of R (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. URL:
216 <https://www.Rproject.org>) and STATA version 18.0. We will compute overall association
217 measures using random-effect models and report I^2 and Tau^2 statistics for heterogeneity
218 (Kirkwood & Sterne, 2003). The evaluation of publication bias will be performed by visually
219 assessing funnel plots (Sterne & Egger, 2001). Additionally, since visually assessment of a
220 funnel plot on its own is not always reliable, the presence of publication bias will be assessed
221 using Egger’s linear regression test.

222 As a sensitivity analysis and to inspect potential sources of heterogeneity, we will stratify the
223 meta-analyses by gender. We will assess whether results are sensitive to study quality by
224 stratifying by ROB status.

225

226 *GRADE*

227 The quality of evidence across studies will be assessed using the Grading of Recommendation
228 Assessment, Developmental and Evaluation (GRADE), which is a recognised approach to
229 systematic and transparent assessment of evidence. The quality of the evidence is graded into
230 four levels: "high", "moderate", "low" or "very low" (Guyatt et al., 2011). There are five criteria
231 that can lead to downgrading of the quality of evidence, which include *risk of bias*,
232 *inconsistency*, *indirect evidence*, *inaccuracy*, and *publication bias*. Furthermore, there are three
233 factors that can lead to upgrading the quality of evidence for each outcome.: *Effect size*, *dose*
234 *response relationship*, and *confounding* (Schünemann H et al., 2013). The GRADEpro software
235 will be used to produce a GRADE evidence table, to provide an overview of the quality and
236 relevant information of each outcome (GRADEpro, 2022)(www.gradepr.org).

237

238 *Data sharing*

239 The bibliographic databases, extracted data, risk of bias assessment and GRADEing will be
240 included in the final publication and its annexes.

241

242 *Protocol Registration*

243 This protocol is registered at the open repository Zenodo.

244

245 *Acknowledgements*

246 We extend our sincere gratitude to a research librarian at Aarhus university library, for their
247 invaluable assistance in navigating the vast array of literature and resources essential to our
248 study.

249

250

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